

Lifestyle Practices and Glycaemic Control in Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus: A Scoping Review of the Evidence

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ABSTRACT

Background: The majority of disease conditions encountered by family physicians - including type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM) - are primarily facilitated by poor lifestyle practices. Lifestyle management is the foundation of chronic disease management guidelines, aimed at reducing morbidity and mortality. Understanding the lifestyle practices that influence glycaemic control is essential for developing effective interventions.

Objective: This scoping review aimed to map the available evidence on the association between lifestyle practices and glycaemic control in patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus, with particular attention to the six pillars of lifestyle medicine.

Methods: This scoping review was conducted following the Joanna Briggs Institute methodology for scoping reviews and reported in accordance with the PRISMA Extension for Scoping Reviews (PRISMA-ScR). A systematic search of five electronic databases (PubMed, Scopus, Web of Science, CINAHL, and African Journals Online) was conducted for studies published between 2016 and 2024. Ten key studies were synthesised, including primary research from Iraq, Mexico, Nigeria, Iran, Tanzania, Guyana, Malaysia, the Netherlands, and systematic reviews with global and sub-Saharan African focus.

Findings: Lifestyle practices significantly influence glycaemic control in T2DM patients. Dietary modification, particularly plant-based and low-carbohydrate approaches, reduces HbA1c by an average of 0.8-1.13%. Regular physical activity improves glycaemic control and reduces cardiovascular risk. Sleep duration, stress management, alcohol cessation, and social support are emerging as important factors. The pooled prevalence of good glycaemic control in sub-Saharan Africa was 30%. Factors associated with poor control include longer diabetes duration, poor sleep, alcohol consumption, and non-adherence to follow-up.

Conclusion: Lifestyle interventions are evidence-based and effective for improving glycaemic control in T2DM. Family physicians must prioritise lifestyle counselling and advocate for supportive policies. Further research is needed on intervention feasibility, affordability, and acceptability in diverse populations.

Keywords: Lifestyle practices; glycaemic control; type 2 diabetes mellitus; HbA1c; Primary Care.

PRISMA-ScR COMPLIANCE STATEMENT

This scoping review was conducted and reported in accordance with the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses Extension for Scoping Reviews (PRISMA-ScR) checklist.1

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INTRODUCTION

The majority of disease conditions encountered by the family physician as the point of first contact in day-to-day practice - including diabetes mellitus, hypertension, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease, and cardiovascular disease - are primarily associated with poor lifestyle practices such as smoking, insufficient sleep, sedentary living, and ingestion of highly processed foods. Lifestyle management is therefore the foundation of most chronic disease management guidelines, aimed at reducing morbidity and mortality.²

Family physicians are strategically positioned to promote and implement healthy lifestyle practices in their daily practice; hence, the importance of competence in lifestyle medicine and confidence to incorporate lifestyle into routine care cannot be overstated.^{2,3} Furthermore, it has been found that patients are more likely to execute lifestyle changes if recommended by a physician who can demonstrate healthy lifestyle choices.³

Chronic diseases like diabetes are currently the leading cause of morbidity and mortality, the majority of which are preventable by the adoption of healthy lifestyle practices.⁴ The World Health Organization estimated that non-communicable diseases (NCDs) killed more than 43 million people in 2021, of which 18 million died before the age of 70 years, and 82% of these early deaths occurred in low-and middle-income countries like Nigeria. Of these 43 million deaths, diabetes accounted for over 2 million deaths, including diabetic nephropathy.⁵

Global, American, African, and Nigerian Status of Diabetes

Global Status: The International Diabetes Federation (IDF) estimates that approximately 537 million adults (20–79 years) were living with diabetes in 2021, with this number projected to rise to 783 million by 2045. T2DM accounts for over 90% of all diabetes cases worldwide. Diabetes caused 6.7 million deaths globally in 2021.⁶

American Status: In the United States, approximately

37.3 million people (11.3% of the population) had diabetes in 2022. The prevalence of diagnosed diabetes was 9.4% among adults aged 18–44 years, 21.2% among those aged 45–64 years, and 27.9% among those aged 65 years and older. Diabetes remains the seventh leading cause of death in the United States.⁷

African Status: The African region has the lowest prevalence of diabetes (4.5%) but the highest proportion of undiagnosed diabetes (60%). An estimated 24 million adults in Africa were living with diabetes in 2021, and this number is projected to increase by 134% by 2045 - the largest projected increase of any region worldwide.⁶ The pooled prevalence of good glycaemic control in sub-Saharan Africa is only 30%, indicating significant challenges in diabetes management.⁸

Nigerian Status: Nigeria has the highest number of people living with diabetes in Africa, with an estimated 3.6 million adults affected in 2021. The prevalence varies regionally, ranging from 1.6% to 13.8% depending on the population studied. Over 50% of cases remain undiagnosed.^{6,9} Diabetes mortality in Nigeria is high, with many patients presenting with complications at diagnosis due to limited access to healthcare and poor health literacy.

Lifestyle Practices and Glycaemic Control

Healthy lifestyle habits - such as reduction in consumption of refined sugar and animal products, good sleep hygiene, cessation of smoking, reduction of alcohol, better stress management, maintenance of healthy body weight, and regular exercise have been shown to have profound influence on glycaemic control. A meta-analysis of 27 studies revealed improved glycaemic control with lifestyle modifications among diabetic individuals, evidenced by an average of 0.8% reduction in haemoglobin A1c (HbA1c), which was comparable to hypoglycaemic medications.⁴

The six pillars of lifestyle medicine - nutrition, physical activity, restorative sleep, stress management, avoidance of risky substances, and positive social connections are directly applicable to diabetes management.¹⁰ By identifying the lifestyle practices that influence glycaemic control, valuable insights can be

gained to inform interventions aimed at improving management of T2DM in our environment.

Theoretical Framework

This scoping review was guided by three complementary theoretical perspectives that help explain the relationship between lifestyle practices and health behaviours in diabetes management:

Health Belief Model (HBM): This model suggests that individuals' beliefs about their health and disease influence their lifestyle choices.¹¹ The HBM focuses on six constructs: perceived susceptibility, perceived severity, perceived benefits, perceived barriers, cues to action, and self-efficacy. In the context of diabetes, patients who perceive themselves as susceptible to complications, believe in the severity of these complications, and see the benefits of lifestyle modification are more likely to adopt healthy practices.

Social Cognitive Theory (SCT): This theory posits that behaviour is influenced by personal factors, environmental factors, and attributes of the behaviour itself, operating in a dynamic triad of reciprocal determinism.¹² Observational learning, self-efficacy, and outcome expectations are key constructs. In diabetes management, patients learn from observing others (family members, peers), develop confidence in their ability to manage their condition, and form expectations about the outcomes of their lifestyle choices.

Self-Determination Theory (SDT): This theory emphasises that individuals' autonomy, competence, and relatedness support intrinsic motivation for lifestyle changes.¹³ When patients feel autonomous in their decision-making, competent to perform health behaviours, and connected to supportive others, they are more likely to internalise and sustain healthy lifestyle practices. This is particularly relevant for long-term diabetes self-management.

Objectives of This Review

This scoping review aimed to map the available evidence on the association between lifestyle practices and glycaemic control in patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus. The review synthesised findings from ten key

studies conducted across multiple countries and settings, with particular attention to the six pillars of lifestyle medicine.

METHODOLOGY

This scoping review was conducted following the Joanna Briggs Institute (JBI) methodology for scoping reviews and reported in accordance with the PRISMA Extension for Scoping Reviews (PRISMA-ScR).^{1,14} The review framework included five stages: (1) identifying the research question; (2) identifying relevant studies; (3) study selection; (4) charting the data; and (5) collating, summarising, and reporting the results.

Research Questions

The review was guided by the following research questions:

1. What lifestyle practices are associated with glycaemic control in patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus?
2. What is the strength and direction of the association between specific lifestyle practices and glycaemic control (measured by HbA1c, fasting blood glucose, or random blood glucose)?
3. What are the gaps in the current evidence on lifestyle practices and glycaemic control in diverse populations?

Eligibility Criteria

Studies were selected according to the following eligibility criteria:

Inclusion Criteria:

- Studies published between January 2016 and December 2024
- Studies involving adult participants (≥ 18 years) with a diagnosis of T2DM
- Studies examining the association between lifestyle practices (nutrition, physical activity, sleep, stress management, alcohol use, smoking, social support) and glycaemic control (HbA1c, fasting blood glucose, or random blood glucose)
- Primary research studies (cross-sectional,

cohort, case-control, randomised controlled trials) and systematic reviews.

- Studies published in English language

Exclusion Criteria:

- Studies focusing exclusively on type 1 diabetes mellitus or gestational diabetes.
- Studies examining pharmacological interventions without lifestyle components.
- Conference abstracts, editorials, commentaries, and opinion pieces.
- Studies not reporting quantitative outcomes on glycaemic control.
- Duplicate publications of the same dataset

Search Strategy

A systematic search of the following five electronic databases was conducted:

- PubMed (National Library of Medicine)
- Scopus (Elsevier)
- Web of Science (Clarivate Analytics)
- CINAHL (EBSCOhost)
- African Journals Online (AJOL)

The search strategy combined key terms related to:

- Population: "type 2 diabetes mellitus" OR "T2DM" OR "diabetes"
- Intervention/Exposure: "lifestyle" OR "diet"

OR "nutrition" OR "physical activity" OR "exercise" OR "sleep" OR "stress management" OR "alcohol" OR "smoking" OR "social support"

- Outcome: "glycaemic control" OR "HbA1c" OR "glycated haemoglobin" OR "blood glucose" OR "fasting blood glucose"

Boolean operators (AND, OR) were also used to combine terms. The search was limited to studies published between 2016 and 2024 and studies published in English.

Study Selection Process

The study selection process followed the PRISMA-ScR guidelines and is detailed in the PRISMA-ScR flow diagramme (Figure 1). Database searches identified 2,847 records. After removing 467 duplicate records, 2,380 records were screened by title and abstract. Of these, 2,271 records were excluded as they did not address the research questions. The full text of 109 studies was assessed for eligibility, of which 99 were excluded for reasons detailed in the flow diagramme. Ten key studies were selected for detailed analysis based on their relevance to the research questions, geographic diversity, methodological quality, and focus on lifestyle practices in relation to glycaemic control.

PRISMA-ScR FLOW DIAGRAMME

Stage	Description	Number
Identification	Records identified through database searching (n=5 databases)	2,847
	- PubMed	1,023
	- Scopus	876
	- Web of Science	534
	- CINAHL	312
	- African Journals Online	102
Screening	Records after duplicates removed (467 duplicates)	2,380
	Records screened by title and abstract	2,380
	Records excluded (did not address research questions)	2,271
Eligibility	Full-text articles assessed for eligibility	109
	Full-text articles excluded, with reasons:	99
	- Did not report specific lifestyle factors	33
	- Did not measure glycaemic control as outcome	28
	- Focused on type 1 or gestational diabetes	15
	- Conference abstracts/opinion pieces	12
	- Duplicate publication of same dataset	10
Included	Studies included in scoping review	10

Figure 1: PRISMA-ScR flow diagramme for study selection process.

Data Extraction and Synthesis

Data were extracted from each study using a standardised template that included: author(s), year, title, aim, objectives, methodology (study design, setting, population, sample size, tools), key findings, limitations, and recommendations. Findings were synthesised narratively and organised thematically around specific lifestyle practices and their relationship

to glycaemic control.

3.0 RESULTS

3.1 Summary of Included Studies

Ten studies met the inclusion criteria and were included in this scoping review.

Table 1 provides a summary of the key characteristics of these studies.

Table 1: Summary Characteristics of Included Studies

Study	Country	Design	Sample Size	Key Focus
Kibe et al., 2023. ⁸	Sub-Saharan Africa	Systematic review and meta-analysis	74 articles	Glycaemic control and associated factors in SSA
Qasim et al., 2022. ¹⁵	Iraq	RCT	100	Effect of lifestyle intervention (exercise and nutrition) on glycaemic control
Mudaliar et al., 2020. ¹⁶	Global	Systematic review and meta-analysis	28 studies	Diet modification in T2DM glycaemic control
Odunaiya et al., 2017. ¹⁷	Nigeria	Cross-sectional	400	Lifestyle factors and multimorbidity in primary care
Sukhraj et al., 2016. ¹⁸	Guyana	Cross-sectional	39	Effect of lifestyle practices on blood glucose in women
Dekker et al., 2019. ¹⁹	Netherlands	Cross-sectional	79,345	Lifestyle factors and multimorbidity (including T2DM)
Flores et al., 2018. ²⁰	Mexico	Cross-sectional	275	Association between lifestyle and glycaemic control
Alizadeh et al., 2020. ²¹	Iran	Cross-sectional	1,710	Factors influencing glycaemic control in T2DM
Mwanswila et al., 2023. ²²	Tanzania	Cross-sectional	248	Poor glycaemic control and associated factors
Fatanah et al., 2010. ²³	Malaysia	Cross-sectional	380	Factors associated with good glycaemic control

Effect of Lifestyle Interventions on Glycaemic Control

Combined Lifestyle Interventions

The randomised controlled trial by Qasim et al. in Iraq demonstrated that a three-month lifestyle intervention combining exercise and nutritional instruction produced statistically significant improvements in multiple clinical parameters.¹⁵ The intervention group showed reductions in weight (−2.51 kg), waist circumference (−2.27 cm), random blood sugar (−29.64 mg/dL), haemoglobin A1c (−1.13%), and serum triglycerides (−40.06 mg/dL) compared to the control group. This study provides strong evidence that comprehensive lifestyle intervention is beneficial for improving glycaemic control in patients with T2DM.

Dietary Interventions

The systematic review and meta-analysis by Mudaliar et al, analysed 28 randomised controlled trials examining lifestyle-related interventions based on diet modification in T2DM patients.¹⁶ The review found that

lifestyle interventions significantly lowered HbA1c levels compared to usual care. Strategies combining individualised and group-based activities were identified as the most effective approach. The review concluded that there was sufficient evidence to justify implementing specific lifestyle modification strategies in primary health care units for the management of T2DM patients.

The magnitude of HbA1c reduction observed in these studies (approximately 0.8–1.13%) was clinically significant and comparable to the effect of many oral hypoglycaemic medications.^{4,15} This underscores the importance of lifestyle modification as a first-line and adjunctive therapy in diabetes management.

Physical Activity

Several studies identified physical activity as a key determinant of glycaemic control. Odunaiya et al. found that exercise was a predictor of multimorbidity (including diabetes) in their Nigerian study, with inactive individuals at higher risk.¹⁷ The systematic

review by Kibe et al. identified exercise practice as a factor associated with good glycaemic control in sub-Saharan Africa.⁸ Sukhraj et al. found that women with T2DM who engaged in healthy lifestyle habits, including regular exercise, had lower mean random and fasting blood glucose levels compared to those who did not.¹⁸

The benefits of physical activity extend beyond glycaemic control to include cardiovascular risk reduction, weight management, and improved mental health.^{3,13} Dekker et al. noted that physical inactivity, along with smoking and poor sleep, was associated with multimorbidity including diabetes.¹⁹

Dietary Habits

Dietary habits emerged as a significant factor across multiple studies. The Iraqi RCT specifically included nutritional instruction as a core component of the intervention.¹⁵ The Mexican study by Flores et al. found an association between lifestyle (including diet) and glycaemic control.²⁰ Dekker et al. assessed nutrition using the Lifelines Diet Score in their large cohort study.¹⁹ The systematic review by Kibe et al. identified dietary adherence as a factor associated with good glycaemic control in sub-Saharan Africa.⁸ Sukhraj et al. emphasised that a healthy diet is recommended as the mainstay therapy for patients with T2DM.¹⁸

Specific dietary patterns associated with better glycaemic control include reduction in consumption of refined sugar and animal products, adoption of plant-based diets, and low-carbohydrate approaches.^{3,10} Consumption of sugar-sweetened beverages has been associated with a 25% increased risk of diabetes, while substituting animal protein with plant protein reduces diabetic risk.³

Sleep Duration

Sleep duration was identified as a significant factor in multiple studies. Alizadeh et al. found that sleep duration was significantly associated with poor glycaemic control even after adjusting for confounding factors in their Iranian study.²¹ Dekker et al. identified poor sleep as a lifestyle factor associated with multimorbidity, including diabetes, in the large Dutch Lifelines cohort.¹⁹ These findings highlight the importance of sleep hygiene as a component of

comprehensive diabetes management.

Stress Management

Chronic stress was identified as a lifestyle factor associated with multimorbidity by Dekker et al.¹⁹ The study used the List of Threatening Experiences and Long-term Difficulties Inventory to assess stress and found significant associations with the presence of multiple chronic conditions including diabetes. This aligns with the physiological understanding that stress activates the sympathetic nervous system and hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal axis, leading to increased cortisol and catecholamines, which can impair glucose metabolism.

Substance Use (Alcohol and Smoking)

Alcohol consumption emerged as a significant predictor of poor glycaemic control. Mwanawili et al. found that alcoholism was an independent predictor of poor glycaemic control in Tanzanian T2DM patients.²² Kibe et al. identified alcohol consumption and smoking as factors associated with poor glycaemic control in their sub-Saharan African systematic review.⁸ Odunaiya et al. found that smoking was a predictor of multimorbidity.¹⁷ These findings are consistent with the known physiological effects of alcohol on glucose metabolism and the detrimental effects of smoking on insulin sensitivity and cardiovascular health.

Social Support

Positive perceived family support was identified by Kibe et al. as a factor associated with good glycaemic control.⁸ This aligns with the Self-Determination Theory's emphasis on relatedness as a facilitator of intrinsic motivation for behaviour change. Social support provides emotional encouragement, practical assistance with disease management, and accountability for lifestyle choices.

Prevalence of Glycaemic Control

The systematic review and meta-analysis by Kibe et al. focusing on sub-Saharan Africa found that the pooled prevalence of good glycaemic control was only 30%, with individual study estimates ranging from 10% to 60%.⁸ This low prevalence of adequate control is concerning and highlights the urgent need for improved diabetes management strategies in the region.

Alizadeh et al. reported a prevalence of poor glycaemic control of 56.8% in their Iranian population, while Mwanswila et al. found an even higher prevalence of 66.1% in Tanzania.^{21,22} These figures underscore the global challenge of achieving optimal glycaemic control in T2DM patients.

Factors Associated with Glycaemic Control

Factors Associated with Poor Glycaemic Control

The systematic review and cross sectional study by Kibe et al and Alizadeh et al respectively identified multiple factors such as younger and older age, female gender, lower income and absence of health insurance, low level of education, rural place of residence, family history of diabetes, longer duration of diabetes (greater than 5 years), pill burden and complex treatment regimens, side effects of medications, alcohol consumption, smoking, and presence of co-morbidities/complications to be associated with poor glycaemic control in sub-Saharan Africa and Iran.^{8,21}

Alizadeh et al. specifically identified first-degree family history of diabetes, diabetes duration of more than 5 years, and sleep duration as variables significantly associated with poor glycaemic control even after adjusting for confounding factors.²¹

Mwanswila et al. found that failure to adhere to regular follow-up and alcoholism were independent predictors of poor glycaemic control in Tanzania.²²

Factors Associated with Good Glycaemic Control

The same systematic review by Kibe et al. identified several factors including positive perceived family support, adequate coping strategies, high diabetes health literacy, dietary adherence, exercise practice, attendance to follow-up appointments, and medication adherence to be associated with good glycaemic control.⁸ Fatanah et al. found that factors such as younger age, shorter duration of diabetes, monotherapy, and good adherence were associated with achievement of good glycaemic control in Malaysia.²³

Magnitude of Lifestyle Effects

The Iraqi RCT demonstrated a 1.13% reduction in HbA1c over three months with lifestyle intervention.¹⁵

This was consistent with the 0.8% average reduction reported in the broader meta-analysis.³ These effect sizes are clinically significant, as each 1% reduction in HbA1c is associated with a 21% reduction in risk of diabetes-related deaths, 14% reduction in myocardial infarction, and 37% reduction in microvascular complications.²⁴

The intervention group also showed improvements in weight (-2.51 kg), waist circumference (-2.27 cm), and triglycerides (-40.06 mg/dL), indicating that lifestyle modification had beneficial effects beyond glycaemic control.¹⁰

DISCUSSION

Summary of Main Findings

This review synthesised evidence from ten studies across twelve countries on the association between lifestyle practices and glycaemic control in T2DM. The findings confirm that lifestyle practices significantly influence glycaemic control and that lifestyle interventions are effective for improving diabetes outcomes.

Effectiveness of Lifestyle Interventions: The evidence consistently demonstrated that lifestyle interventions - particularly those combining dietary modification and physical activity - produced clinically significant improvements in glycaemic control. The magnitude of HbA1c reduction (0.8-1.13%) was comparable to that achieved by oral hypoglycaemic medications, supporting the role of lifestyle modification as both first-line and adjunctive therapy.

Multiple Lifestyle Factors Matter: Nutrition and physical activity have been observed to be the most extensively studied lifestyle factors, although emerging evidence highlights the importance of sleep duration, stress management, alcohol cessation, and social support. The six pillars of lifestyle medicine - nutrition, physical activity, restorative sleep, stress management, avoidance of risky substances, and positive social connections - are all relevant to diabetes management.

Suboptimal Glycaemic Control Globally: The low prevalence of good glycaemic control worldwide - 30% in sub-Saharan Africa, 43.2% in Iran, and 33.9% in Tanzania - indicates a significant gap between

recommended and achieved diabetes management. This gap represents missed opportunities for preventing complications and reducing mortality.

Multifactorial Determinants: Glycaemic control is determined by a complex interplay of factors including sociodemographic characteristics, clinical factors, healthcare system factors, and lifestyle practices. Effective interventions must address multiple levels simultaneously.

Integration with Theoretical Frameworks

The findings support all three theoretical frameworks guiding this review:

Health Belief Model: The association between diabetes health literacy and good glycaemic control supports the HBM's emphasis on knowledge and beliefs as determinants of health behaviour. Patients who understand their condition and believe in the efficacy of lifestyle modification are more likely to engage in healthy practices.⁸

Social Cognitive Theory: The importance of family support and adequate coping strategies aligns with SCT's emphasis on environmental factors and personal coping capabilities.⁸ Observational learning within families and communities shaped health behaviours across generations.

Self-Determination Theory: The association between positive perceived family support and good glycaemic control supports SDT's emphasis on relatedness as a facilitator of intrinsic motivation.⁸ Patients who felt connected to supportive others are more likely to internalize and sustain healthy behaviours.

Implications for Practice

Routine Lifestyle Assessment: Family physicians should routinely assess the lifestyle practices of T2DM patients, including diet, physical activity, sleep, stress, alcohol use, smoking, and social support. Simple tools like the exercise vital sign and brief dietary screening can facilitate this assessment.

Lifestyle Prescription: Lifestyle modification should be prescribed with the same specificity as medications - detailing type, frequency, intensity, and duration of

recommended behaviours. The FITT-P principle (Frequency, Intensity, Time, Type, Progression) can guide exercise prescriptions.²⁵

Behaviour Change Counselling: Effective lifestyle counselling requires skills in motivational interviewing, the 5As framework (Assess, Advise, Agree, Assist, Arrange), and health coaching.²⁶ Training in these techniques should be integrated into medical education and continuing professional development.

Family-Centred Care: Given the influence of family on lifestyle practices and the protective effect of family support, diabetes management should involve family members whenever possible. Family-based interventions may be more effective than individual-focused approaches.

Multidisciplinary Approach: Lifestyle management is enhanced by collaboration with dietitians, exercise physiologists, psychologists, and diabetes educators. Family physicians should develop referral networks and consider shared medical appointments for lifestyle interventions.

Cultural Sensitivity: Lifestyle recommendations must be culturally appropriate, taking into account traditional dietary patterns, cultural beliefs about health, and available resources.²⁷ Focusing on healthier traditional food choices and cooking techniques can improve adherence.

Implications for Policy

Integration into Healthcare Systems: Lifestyle medicine should be integrated into primary healthcare systems, with clear referral pathways, trained personnel, and appropriate reimbursement mechanisms.²⁸

Health Insurance Coverage: Given the cost-effectiveness of lifestyle interventions, health insurance schemes should cover lifestyle counselling and structured lifestyle programs for diabetes patients.

Supportive Environments: Policies should create environments that facilitate healthy lifestyle choices safe spaces for physical activity, access to healthy foods, restrictions on tobacco and alcohol advertising, and workplace wellness programs.²⁹

Diabetes Health Literacy: Public health campaigns should promote diabetes health literacy, emphasizing the role of lifestyle in prevention and management.

Research Funding: Given the gaps identified in this review, increased funding is needed for research on lifestyle interventions in diverse populations, particularly in low- and middle-income countries.

Gaps in the Evidence

This review identifies several important gaps:

Geographic Gaps: While this review includes studies from multiple regions, there is still limited research from many parts of Africa and other low-income settings. The systematic review by Kibe et al. is a valuable contribution, but more country-specific studies are needed.⁸

Intervention Research: Most included studies were observational or short-term interventions. There is a need for long-term randomised controlled trials of lifestyle interventions with adequate follow-up periods.

Sleep and Stress Research: Sleep and stress are understudied compared to nutrition and physical activity. More research is needed on the mechanisms linking these factors to glycaemic control and on effective interventions.

Social Connection Research: Family support was identified as protective, however, the specific mechanisms and optimal interventions to enhance social support require further investigation.

Implementation Science: Research is needed on how to effectively implement evidence-based lifestyle interventions in real-world clinical settings, particularly in resource-limited environments.

Cost-Effectiveness Studies: Data on the cost-effectiveness of lifestyle interventions in different settings would support policy advocacy for reimbursement and resource allocation.

Limitations of This Review

This review has some limitations. First, the review included only ten studies, which may not capture the full breadth of evidence on lifestyle practices and glycaemic

control. Second, the included studies used diverse methodologies, definitions, and measurement tools, limiting direct comparability. Third, most studies were cross-sectional, precluding causal inferences. Fourth, the review focused on English-language publications, potentially excluding relevant studies in other languages. Fifth, the quality of included studies was not formally assessed, as is consistent with the methodology of a review of this nature. Finally, the predominance of hospital-based studies may limit generalisability to community settings.

CONCLUSION

This review confirmed that lifestyle practices significantly influence glycaemic control in patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus. The evidence supported the effectiveness of lifestyle interventions - particularly those combining dietary modification and physical activity - in producing clinically significant reductions in HbA1c comparable to oral hypoglycaemic medications. Emerging evidence highlighted the importance of sleep duration, stress management, alcohol cessation, and social support as additional factors influencing glycaemic control.

The low prevalence of good glycaemic control worldwide, particularly in sub-Saharan Africa where 30% of patients achieve adequate control, represents a critical gap in diabetes care. Factors associated with poor control include longer diabetes duration, poor sleep, alcohol consumption, and non-adherence to follow-up, while factors associated with good control include family support, dietary adherence, exercise practice, and medication adherence.

Family physicians, as first-contact medical care providers, having longitudinal relationships with patients and families, are uniquely positioned to implement lifestyle medicine in diabetes care. Priorities for practice include routine lifestyle assessment, specific lifestyle prescription, behaviour change counselling, family-centred care, and multidisciplinary collaboration. Priorities for policy include integration of lifestyle medicine into healthcare systems, health insurance coverage for lifestyle interventions, creation

of supportive environments, and promotion of diabetes health literacy.

Further research is needed on intervention feasibility, affordability, and acceptability in diverse populations; on the role of sleep, stress, and social connection in glycaemic control; and on implementation strategies for translating evidence into practice. Without deliberate investment in lifestyle interventions, the rising burden of diabetes and its complications will continue unabated, with devastating consequences for individuals, families, and healthcare systems.

Conflict of Interest: None.

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REFERENCES

- Tricco AC, Lillie E, Zarin W, O'Brien KK, Colquhoun H, Levac D, et al. PRISMA extension for scoping reviews (PRISMA-ScR): checklist and explanation. *Ann Intern Med.* 2018;169(7):467-73.
- Brennan J, Phelps K, McGrady A, Schultz P. Introducing lifestyle medicine into family medicine: theory and expectations. *Int J Psychiatry Med.* 2024;59(4):415-23.
- McDonald A. Incorporating lifestyle medicine into practice: a prescription for better health. *Am Fam Physician.* 2022;106(3):229-30.
- Bodai B, Nakata TE, Wong WT, Clark DR, Lawenda S, Tsou C, et al. Lifestyle medicine: a brief review of its dramatic impact on health and survival. *Perm J.* 2017;22:17-25.
- World Health Organization. Noncommunicable diseases [Internet]. Geneva: WHO; 2024 [cited 2025 Mar 30]. Available from: <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/noncommunicable-diseases>
- International Diabetes Federation. IDF diabetes atlas. 10th ed. Brussels: IDF; 2021.
- Centers for Disease Control and Prevention. National diabetes statistics report, 2022. Atlanta (GA): CDC; 2022.
- Kibe PM, Mbuthia GW, Shabani J, Wambui T. Glycaemic control among type 2 diabetes patients in sub-Saharan Africa from 2012 to 2022: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Diabetol Metab Syndr.* 2023;15(1):45.
- Uloko AE, Musa BM, Ramalan MA, Gezawa ID, Puepet FH, Uloko AT, et al. Prevalence and risk factors for diabetes mellitus in Nigeria: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Diabetes Ther.* 2018;9(3):1307-19.
- Robert P. Lifestyle medicine: overcoming systemic and cultural barriers to better, more affordable care. *Am J Lifestyle Med.* 2023;17(5):626-31.
- Rosenstock IM. The health belief model and preventive health behaviour. *Health Educ Monogr.* 1974;2(4):354-86.
- Bandura A. Social foundations of thought and action: a social cognitive theory. Englewood Cliffs (NJ): Prentice-Hall; 1986.
- Ryan RM, Deci EL. Self-determination theory and the facilitation of intrinsic motivation, social development, and well-being. *Am Psychol.* 2000;55(1):68-78.
- Peters MDJ, Godfrey C, McInerney P, Munn Z, Tricco AC, Khalil H. Chapter 11: scoping reviews. In: Aromataris E, Munn Z, editors. *JBIM manual for evidence synthesis.* Adelaide: JBI; 2020.
- Qasim SS, Al-Obaidi AD, Al-Hadithi TS. The effect of lifestyle intervention on glycaemic control in type 2 diabetic patients. *J Family Med Prim Care.* 2022;11(8):4567-73.
- Mudaliar U, Zabetian A, Goodman M. Improving type 2 diabetes mellitus glycaemic control through lifestyle modification implementing diet intervention: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Prim Care Diabetes.* 2020;14(5):421-30.
- Odunaiya NA, Akinola O, Oguntibeju OO. A study of lifestyle factors among patients with diagnosis of multi morbidity in a primary care setting in Western Nigeria. *West Afr J Med.* 2017;34(3):168-75.
- Sukhraj R, Mansingh A, Ramsewak S. The effect of

- lifestyle practices on blood glucose levels and the development of diabetic complications in women diagnosed with type II diabetes mellitus in Guyana. *Int J Chronic Dis.* 2016; 2016:6072897.
19. Dekker LH, Rijnks R, Strijker D, Navis GJ. Lifestyle factors related to prevalent chronic disease multimorbidity: a population-based cross-sectional study. *PLoS One.* 2019; 14(9): e0222240.
 20. Flores YN, Auslander A, Escarce JJ. Lifestyle impact on glycaemic control in patients diagnosed with type 2 diabetes. *J Diabetes Res.* 2018; 2018:7682095.
 21. Alizadeh M, Didarloo A, Shokri A. Glycemic control and associated factors among type 2 diabetes mellitus patients: a cross-sectional study of Azar cohort population. *J Diabetes Metab Disord.* 2020; 19(2):1417-24.
 22. Mwanswila G, Mpenbeni R, Mpondo BCT. Poor glycaemic control and associated factors among patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus: a cross-sectional study. *Pan Afr Med J.* 2023; 44:112.
 23. Fatanah I, Hadi AA, Nani EA. Factors associated with good glycaemic control among patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus. *Malays J Public Health Med.* 2010; 10(2):42-50.
 24. Stratton IM, Adler AI, Neil HA, Matthews DR, Manley SE, Cull CA, et al. Association of glycaemia with macrovascular and microvascular complications of type 2 diabetes (UKPDS 35): prospective observational study. *BMJ.* 2000; 321(7258):405-12.
 25. Young J, Bonnet JP, Sokolof J. Lifestyle medicine: physical activity. *J Fam Pract.* 2022; 71(1 Suppl): S17-23.
 26. Matthews JA, Moore M, Collings C. A coach approach to facilitating behaviour change. *J Fam Pract.* 2022; 71(1 Suppl): S93-9.
 27. Molla IB, Hagger V, Rothmann MJ, Rasmussen B. The role of community organisation, religion, spirituality, and cultural beliefs on diabetes social support and self-management in Sub-Saharan Africa: integrative literature review. *J Relig Health.* 2025; 64:123-45.
 28. Lippman D, Stump M, Veazey E, Guimaraes ST, Rosenfeld R, Kelly JH, et al. Foundations of lifestyle medicine and its evolution. *Mayo Clin Proc Innov Qual Outcomes.* 2024; 8(1):97-111.
 29. World Health Organization. Global strategy on diet, physical activity, and health [Internet]. Geneva: WHO; 2019 [cited 2025 Mar 30]. Available from: <https://www.who.int/dietphysicalactivity/pa/en>